

PRIME

Project Indicators for Urgent Care and Emergency Medicine

Fenice Coordination Centre

7 May 2024

Summary

The Fenice Group.....	3
The project proposal	3
Project indicators for urgent care and emergency medicine services (prime).....	3
Quality of care indicators in the emergency room.....	4
Indicator 1 - Boarding.....	6
Indicator 2 - ED crowding	7
Indicator 3 - Reassessment of patients waiting for the first medical or nursing assessment.....	8
Indicator 4 - Waiting time from arrival at ED to first medical/nursing assessment, and visit duration	9
Indicator 5 - Patient management during the waiting time for the first assessment	10
Indicator 6 - Appropriateness of the fast-track route.....	11
Indicator 7 - Identification of patient with possible sepsis	12
Indicator 8 - Clinical appropriateness of brain CT scan use in mild head injury patients.....	13
Indicator 9 - Clinical appropriateness of the use of CT scan without abdominal contrast medium.....	14
Indicator 10 - Clinical appropriateness of the use of pulmonary CT scan for the diagnosis of pulmonary embolism.....	15
Indicator 11 - Clinical appropriateness in the management of the unstable patient	16
Indicator 12 - Clinical appropriateness in the management of a patient with sepsis	17
Indicator 13 - Bladder catheter placement	18
Indicator 14 - Frequency of falls in elderly patients.....	19
Indicator 15 - Blood culture contamination.....	20
Indicator 16 - Appropriateness of admission for patients with abdominal pain	21
Indicator 17 - Appropriateness of admission for patients with chest pain	22
Indicator 18 - Appropriateness of admission for patients with transient loss of consciousness	23
Indicator 19 - Appropriateness of admission for patients with dyspnoea	24
Appendix.....	25
Composite indicator.....	25
Crowding indicator	26

THE FENICE GROUP

Fenice (Italian Group for Clinical Research in Emergency Medicine) is a network of Italian Emergency Departments and High-Dependency Care Units co-ordinated by the Laboratory of Clinical Epidemiology of the Istituto di Ricerche Farmacologiche Mario Negri IRCCS, which was set up with the aim of promoting and carrying out independent research projects oriented towards the evaluation and improvement of the quality of care and a more rational use of resources.

THE PROJECT PROPOSAL

The Emergency Department (ED) represents the most important point of contact between the national healthcare service and the health needs of citizens, representing the first gateway to the hospital. It is therefore crucial to ensure the proper evaluation and continuous improvement of the quality of the service provided, both in terms of operation and care. To date, however, the evaluation of the quality of the ED has focused solely on aspects of organisational efficiency, conveying the (erroneous) message that the ED is a place of service provision rather than a context of care and assistance. This view has certainly impoverished the specialty and has limited the prospect of improvement to very narrow and unmotivating areas for staff.

In this context, the Fenice group proposed a project to study the quality of care in emergency departments by sharing and analysing their data. This project involves professionals and their respective hospitals and aims to guide the clinical governance at the regional level in promoting interventions to improve the ED that also enhance the care dimension.

The collaborative group's project proposal, which has been submitted to various regional administrations and hospitals for evaluation, has now been formally activated for the Piedmont EDs, thanks to the close collaboration between the Piedmont region's Azienda Zero and the Fenice coordinating centre (Resolution 238/01.00/2023 of 28/11/2023).

PROJECT INDICATORS FOR URGENT CARE AND EMERGENCY MEDICINE SERVICES (PRIME)

Fenice has developed a proposal to monitor the quality of care in Emergency Departments: the PRIME project. The project, which builds on what the Laboratory of Clinical Epidemiology of the Mario Negri Institute has carried out with intensive care wards in the past, foresees four successive phases:

1) **Planning.** In this phase, the regional technical coordination group, made up of representatives of the regional health department, health professionals, and hospitals, draws up the list of indicators that it considers essential and a priority for the current year, in order to represent the quality of care in the ED. For each indicator, the group simultaneously draws up criteria defining desirable thresholds for improvement. These thresholds may be univocal (and therefore common to all the EDs), when based on clear evidence from the literature, or different for each ED (in relation to the initial value of the indicator).

2) **Planning of the objectives.** In this second phase, which takes place at the beginning of the year, each hospital receives a customised report containing, for all the indicators identified by the regional technical coordination group, the values calculated on the basis of its own data for the previous year. Taking into account the report received, each hospital chooses from this list a predetermined number of indicators (in the previous experience with the intensive care units two indicators were chosen) on which to set improvement objectives for the coming year. Within this framework, the region can also choose to set a mandatory threshold for one or two indicators that it considers to be essential. In this

case, for EDs with one or both of these indicators below the threshold, the choice would be automatic. The following is an example to illustrate this concept: suppose the region has placed a special focus on the indicator "median boarding time" and has set a mandatory threshold of 2 hours. This means that all EDs with a median boarding time of more than 2 hours would automatically be assigned the improvement target on this indicator and would only be able to choose the second indicator on which to place the improvement target.

3) Improvement interventions. The third phase is the responsibility of the hospitals and, in particular, of their EDs. In this phase each centre implements interventions to improve the chosen (or assigned) indicators and achieve the established objectives. This phase requires a specific capacity for data and context analysis and specific operational skills. It should be noted that the desired improvement in the indicators is sometimes achieved through the involvement of other hospital departments (once again, think of boarding time). In this sense, the active role of the hospital management is of primary importance for the achievement of the objective.

4) Evaluation. The fourth phase is dedicated to the evaluation of the result achieved by each hospital on the two indicators chosen (or assigned) as improvement targets. At the same time that the target's achievement is checked, each hospital also receives a customised report on the indicators to be chosen for the following year.

In order to be able to implement the project, it will be necessary to adapt the computer applications of the EDs in the region so that they can collect the variables needed to calculate the planned indicators, and to set up automatic synchronisation of the data with the regional servers, in compliance with data protection regulations. In this regard, the number of indicators chosen at the regional level may need to be increased gradually, over time, as the applications are progressively adapted.

This would, on the one hand, ensure that the indicators are, in any case, chosen from a list established by the region according to the priorities decided on, and, on the other hand, would promote a strong sense of responsibility on the part of the hospitals towards improving the chosen indicators.

There are, in fact, at least three conditions that make it possible to implement a serious programme to improve the quality of healthcare:

- 1) the readiness of emergency doctors to discuss and share within their hospitals and with the region the data collected and the related analyses;
- 2) a rigorous and impartial analysis of the data collected from emergency rooms, conducted by an independent group, aimed at evaluating outcomes and identifying areas of criticality on which to invest;
- 3) the concrete possibility for health authorities to direct resources where necessary according to criteria of organisational appropriateness.

QUALITY OF CARE INDICATORS IN THE EMERGENCY ROOM

The initial project proposal and the corresponding list of indicators were revised thanks to the contribution of professionals in the field of urgent care and emergency medicine from all over Italy through a dedicated discussion at the annual meeting of the Fenice group in 2022 and, subsequently, during 2023, through discussions with representatives of the Italian Federation of Healthcare and Hospital Authorities (FIASO). The result of these comparisons was brought to the technical table set up in collaboration with the Piedmont region's Azienda Zero, which revised the quality indicators to be constantly monitored. The indicators were classified into 6 macro-categories: integration with other care services, organisational process, clinical triage process, clinical process when a patient is taken on board, care process, and

appropriateness of hospitalisation.

The proposed indicators are summarised in Table 1 and subsequently described in detail. For each indicator, the rationale, the data needed for the calculation, and what the ED's objective should be when faced with the result (e.g., increase the value of the indicator, reduce the value, reduce the value, but not fall below a specified safety threshold) are given.

With regard to the macro-category appropriateness of hospitalisation (and its four indicators), the definition of appropriate hospitalisation is based on an algorithm developed within the framework of another Fenice project, the Appropriateness of Hospitalisation project. The study protocol, along with additional information, can be found on the project webpage at the following [link](#). At the time of writing, the algorithm was in the validation phase. The four indicators based on this algorithm will therefore only be calculable at the end of this phase.

Table 1. Indicators identified by the Fenice collaborative group for assessing the quality of care in emergency rooms.

<p>Integration with the outside world (2)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Boarding - Crowding <p>Organisational process (3)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Re-evaluation of waiting patients - Waiting time from arrival at ED to first medical/ nursing assessment, and visit duration - Management of patient during waiting time for visit <p>Triage process (2)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fast-track allocation - Identification of patient with possible sepsis <p>Clinical process (5)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Brain CT use in patients with mild head injury - Use of abdominal CT scan without contrast medium - Use of pulmonary CT scan for diagnosis of pulmonary embolism - Management of unstable patient - Management of patient with sepsis 	<p>Nursing care process (3)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Bladder catheter placement - Frequency of falls in the elderly patient - Contamination of blood cultures <p>Appropriateness of hospitalisation (4)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Appropriateness of admissions, patients with abdominal pain - Appropriateness of admissions, patients with chest pain - Appropriateness of admissions, patients with loss of consciousness - Appropriateness of admissions, patients with dyspnoea
---	--

Indicator 1 - Boarding

<u>Calculation</u>	Median boarding time. The boarding time is calculated only for patients admitted to the same hospital in which the ED is situated or transferred to another hospital, and is approximated by the time elapsed from 6 hours after medical or nursing admission to the time of hospital admission or transfer. Patients admitted to the short-stay observation unit are excluded from the calculation. For patients discharged 42 hours or more after having been taken on board (i.e., after first medical or nursing assessment), the time elapsed from 6 hours after being taken on board to the time of discharge is considered as boarding time.
<u>Data required</u>	Date and time of patient admission, medical or nursing (T1); date and time of end of ED service (T3); admission of patient to short-stay observation unit; outcome at end of ED service (discharge/re-hospitalisation in the same hospital/transfer to another hospital).
<u>Type</u>	Integration with the outside world.
<u>Rationale</u>	In-patients should not have to wait for a bed in the ED, except for the minimum time necessary for bed preparation and completion of paperwork.
<u>Objective</u>	Reduce the score from the previous year's value.
<u>Notes</u>	The boarding time corresponds to the time elapsed from the moment the decision is made to admit the patient to the moment of admission. The approximation described in the calculation of the indicator is proposed because it is necessary to assess the availability and, in particular, the reliability of the data on the time at which the decision to hospitalise is made in the EDs participating in the project. If the reliability of this figure in the participating EDs is verified, the approximation of the boarding time will be replaced by the calculation of the corrected time.

Indicator 2 - ED crowding

<u>Calculation</u>	Percentage of time during the last year that the ED crowding indicator (see appendix) was greater than 4, which corresponds to an average waiting time of more than 90 minutes for a clinician or nurse to take on board code 2 or 3 patients.
<u>Data required</u>	Overcrowding indicator of the ED; patients present in the ED hour by hour, broken down by priority code.
<u>Type</u>	Integration with the outside world.
<u>Rationale</u>	The ED should handle a number of patients compatible with its resources so that it doesn't overload the system to the point where the waiting time for code 2 or 3 patients becomes excessive (over 90 minutes).
<u>Objective</u>	Reduce the indicator with respect to the previous year.

Indicator 3 - Reassessment of patients waiting for the first medical or nursing assessment

<u>Calculation</u>	Percentage of patients waiting for the first medical or nursing assessment who are not re-evaluated within the recommended maximum waiting time for the assigned triage code, out of the total number of patients who have exceeded this waiting time, for patients with triage code 2, 3, 4 or 5.
<u>Data required</u>	Reassessment of patients waiting for the first medical or nursing assessment; time of reassessment of patients waiting for the first medical or nursing assessment; time of triage; time of admission; triage code.
<u>Type</u>	Organisational appropriateness of the ED.
<u>Rationale</u>	Patients waiting for the first medical or nursing assessment should be re-evaluated periodically if they remain waiting for longer than the recommended time for the assigned triage code.
<u>Objective</u>	Reduce the score from the previous year's value.

Indicator 4 - Waiting time from arrival at ED to first medical/nursing assessment, and visit duration

<u>Calculation</u>	Composite score (see appendix), derived from the combination of two independent indicators, the first represented by the median waiting time for first medical or nursing assessment over the total number of patients with triage codes 2, 3 or 4, the second related to the median length of stay in the ED for discharged patients (from triage until discharge), again over the total number of patients with triage codes 2, 3 or 4.
<u>Data required</u>	Triage code; time of triage; time of first (medical or nursing) assessment; time of discharge from ED; time of transfer to short-stay observation unit.
<u>Type</u>	Organisational appropriateness of the ED.
<u>Rationale</u>	Patients should be admitted as quickly as possible and their clinical management in the ED should be rapid, but not rushed.
<u>Objective</u>	Reduce the score from the previous year's value (see appendix), but without reducing the median time spent in the ED to below 30 minutes.

Indicator 5 - Patient management during the waiting time for the first assessment

<u>Calculation</u>	Percentage of drop-outs while waiting for care (medical or nursing), out of the total number of patients with code 2, 3, 4. The indicator can also be calculated per priority code.
<u>Data required</u>	Time elapsed between triage (T0) and clinician or nurse visit (T1); triage code.
<u>Type</u>	Clinical appropriateness of triage.
Rationale	After triage, the patient awaiting care should still be followed up to intercept any needs or problems.
<u>Objective</u>	Reduce the score from the previous year's value.

Indicator 6 - Appropriateness of the fast-track route

Calculation	Percentage of patients departing the ED (discharged, transferred or admitted to hospital), out of the total number of patients sent to the fast-track.
<u>Data required</u>	Activation of fast-track route; discharge of patient by ED or fast-track doctor.
<u>Type</u>	Clinical appropriateness of triage and organisational appropriateness.
<u>Rationale</u>	Fast-track patients should have problems that are entirely manageable by the fast-track specialist.
<u>Objective</u>	Reduce the score from the previous year's value.

Indicator 7 - Identification of patient with possible sepsis

<u>Calculation</u>	Percentage of patients with a priority code of 3, 4 or 5 assigned at triage, out of the total number of patients diagnosed with sepsis at discharge from the ED.
<u>Data required</u>	Triage code; discharge diagnosis from ED.
<u>Type</u>	Clinical appropriateness of triage.
<u>Rationale</u>	Sepsis is considered a time-dependent condition. At triage, a clinical picture compatible with sepsis should be appropriately recognised and the patient given a high priority.
<u>Objective</u>	Reduce the score from the previous year's value.

Indicator 8 - Clinical appropriateness of brain CT scan use in mild head injury patients

<u>Calculation</u>	Composite score (see appendix), derived from the combination of two independent indicators: 1) the standardised percentage of mild head injury patients who did not undergo a brain CT scan in the ED and with a neurological diagnosis present in a hospital discharge form for an admission made within 120 hours of arrival, out of the total number of mild head injury patients who did not undergo a brain CT scan in the ED, and 2) the standardised number of brain CT scans performed in the ED on patients with mild head injury to identify one patient with a diagnosis of brain pathology in the hospital discharge form for an admission made within 120 hours of arrival. The composite score is given by the square root of the sum of the squares of the two indicators.
<u>Data required</u>	Diagnosis on exit from the ED for recognition of mild head injury; performance of brain CT scan in the ED; date and time of performance of brain CT scan in the ED; admission within 120 hours of arrival in the ED; hospital discharge form of any admission within 120 hours of admission to the ED.
<u>Type</u>	Clinical appropriateness of care.
<u>Rationale</u>	The most appropriate use of brain CT scans in mild head injury patients is to select those patients with a higher probability of having a brain injury, thus avoiding exposing patients with a very low probability to unnecessary radiation. Both indicators that make up the score will hopefully be reduced. Reducing the first indicator means having correctly identified patients who should not be subjected to brain CT scans. Reducing the second one means having been able to properly select patients for brain CT scans.
<u>Objective</u>	To reduce the score from the previous year's value (see appendix).

Indicator 9 - Clinical appropriateness of the use of CT scan without abdominal contrast medium

<u>Calculation</u>	Among patients who underwent abdominal CT scans without contrast medium, the percentage of patients who underwent abdominal CT scans with contrast medium within 96 hours of the CT scans without contrast medium (patients who underwent both CT scans at the same time are excluded).
<u>Data required</u>	Performance of abdomen CT scan in the ED with specification of contrast medium (if any); date and time of performance of abdomen CT scan in the ED.
<u>Type</u>	Clinical appropriateness of care.
<u>Rationale</u>	The use of abdomen CT scan without contrast medium should be limited to very few clinical problems, which must be adequately identified.
<u>Objective</u>	Reduce the score from the previous year's value.

Indicator 10 - Clinical appropriateness of the use of pulmonary CT scan for the diagnosis of pulmonary embolism

<u>Calculation</u>	Ratio between number of pulmonary CT scans performed for suspected pulmonary embolism (PE) and number of patients with pulmonary CT scans performed in the ED for suspected PE in whom the diagnosis of PE is present in the hospital discharge form or the ED discharge diagnosis.
<u>Data needed</u>	Pulmonary CT scan performed in the ED; motivation for requesting pulmonary CT scan in the ED; date and time of pulmonary CT scan performed in the ED; hospital discharge form of any hospitalisation within 96 hours of admission to the ED; diagnosis of discharge from the ED.
<u>Type</u>	Clinical appropriateness of care.
<u>Rationale</u>	The most appropriate use of pulmonary CT scans in patients with suspected PE is to select the patients with the highest probability of diagnosis, while avoiding exposing patients with very low probability to unnecessary radiation.
<u>Objective</u>	To bring the score within the interquartile range of the regional distribution.

Indicator 11 - Clinical appropriateness in the management of the unstable patient

<u>Calculation</u>	Percentage of patients transferred to a monitored bed (intensive care unit, high-dependency care unit, cardiac intensive care unit, respiratory intensive care unit, ...) within 24 hours of admission, out of the total number of patients admitted from the ED to a non-monitored bed. Patients transferred to the intensive care unit after surgery should be excluded from the numerator.
<u>Data needed</u>	Hospital admission as an outcome of the ED; date and time of admission; department of admission from ED; transfer to monitored bed after admission; date and time of transfer; department of transfer.
<u>Type</u>	Clinical appropriateness of care.
<u>Rationale</u>	The objective of the ED in cases of unstable patients is to manage and stabilise them in order to admit them to the most appropriate ward (<i>work to admit</i>).
<u>Objective</u>	Reduce the score from the previous year's value.

Indicator 12 - Clinical appropriateness in the management of a patient with sepsis

<u>Calculation</u>	Third quartile of time between triage and first blood culture in patients admitted for sepsis.
<u>Data needed</u>	Triage time; time of blood culture collection; admission to hospital as an outcome of ED; sepsis among ED discharge diagnoses.
<u>Type</u>	Clinical appropriateness of care.
<u>Rationale</u>	A blood culture should be performed as soon as possible in patients with sepsis.
<u>Objective</u>	To bring the score to a value of 3 hours or less, as recommended by the guidelines.

Indicator 13 - Bladder catheter placement

<u>Calculation</u>	Percentage of patients for whom a bladder catheter was placed among male stroke and/or femur fracture patients.
<u>Data required</u>	Performance of bladder catheterisation; sex of patient; discharge diagnosis from ED.
<u>Type</u>	Care process.
<u>Rationale</u>	The bladder catheter should only be placed if there is a specific indication for catheterisation. In particular, in the pathologies identified by the indicator, the number of catheters placed should be limited.
<u>Objective</u>	Reduce the value of the indicator.

Indicator 14 - Frequency of falls in elderly patients

<u>Calculation</u>	Incidence of falls in patients aged 65 years and over. The incidence, expressed in number of falls per hospital day, is to be calculated as the ratio of the number of falls observed in this group of patients to the sum of the length of stay in the ED (in days, short-stay observation unit included) of all patients aged 65 years and over.
<u>Data needed</u>	Number of falls and length of stay in the ED of patients aged 65 years and over.
<u>Type</u>	Care process.
<u>Rationale</u>	Preventive measures must be put in place to prevent falls in the ED, especially in elderly patients.
<u>Objective</u>	Reduce the value of the indicator.

Indicator 15 - Blood culture contamination

<u>Calculation</u>	Percentage of contaminated blood cultures out of total number of blood cultures performed in the ED.
<u>Data required</u>	Number of blood cultures contaminated; number of blood cultures performed.
<u>Type</u>	Care process.
<u>Rationale</u>	Contamination of blood cultures can cause a delay in diagnosis and treatment, an extended stay in the ED, and increased costs.
<u>Objective</u>	Reduce the value of the indicator.

Indicator 16 - Appropriateness of admission for patients with abdominal pain

<u>Calculation</u>	Composite score (see appendix), derived from the combination of two independent indicators: 1) the proportion of inappropriate hospitalisations of patients with abdominal pain, and 2) the proportion of patients with abdominal pain inappropriately discharged home. The composite score is given by the square root of the sum of the squares of the two indicators.
<u>Data needed</u>	Abdominal pain at triage; appropriateness of admissions of patients with abdominal pain; appropriateness of discharges of patients with abdominal pain.
<u>Type</u>	Clinical appropriateness of care.
<u>Rationale</u>	Admission and discharge of patients with abdominal pain should be as appropriate as possible.
<u>Objective</u>	Reduce the score from the previous year's value (see appendix).
<u>Notes</u>	This indicator will only be proposed once the corresponding algorithm for assessing the appropriateness of admissions developed by Fenice has been validated.

Indicator 17 - Appropriateness of admission for patients with chest pain

<u>Calculation</u>	Composite score (see appendix), derived from the combination of two independent indicators: 1) the rate of inappropriate admissions of patients with chest pain, and 2) the rate of inappropriate discharges of patients with chest pain. The composite score is given by the square root of the sum of the squares of the two indicators.
<u>Data needed</u>	Thoracic pain at triage; appropriateness of admissions of patients with chest pain; appropriateness of discharges of patients with chest pain.
<u>Type</u>	Clinical appropriateness of care.
<u>Rationale</u>	Admission and discharge of patients with chest pain should be as appropriate as possible.
<u>Objective</u>	Reduce the score from the previous year's value (see appendix).
<u>Notes</u>	This indicator will only be proposed once the corresponding algorithm for assessing the appropriateness of admissions developed by Fenice has been validated.

Indicator 18 - Appropriateness of admission for patients with transient loss of consciousness

<u>Calculation</u>	Composite score (see appendix), derived from the combination of two independent indicators: 1) the rate of inappropriate admissions of patients with transient loss of consciousness, and 2) the rate of inappropriate discharges of patients with transient loss of consciousness. The composite score is given by the square root of the sum of the squares of the two indicators.
<u>Data needed</u>	Transient loss of consciousness at triage; appropriateness of admissions of patients with transient loss of consciousness; appropriateness of discharges of patients with transient loss of consciousness.
<u>Type</u>	Clinical appropriateness of care.
<u>Rationale</u>	Admission and discharge of patients with transient loss of consciousness should be as appropriate as possible.
<u>Objective</u>	To reduce the score from the previous year's value (see appendix).
<u>Notes</u>	This indicator will only be proposed once the corresponding algorithm for assessing the appropriateness of admissions developed by Fenice has been validated.

Indicator 19 - Appropriateness of admission for patients with dyspnoea

<u>Calculation</u>	Composite score (see appendix), derived from the combination of two independent indicators: 1) the rate of inappropriate admissions of patients with dyspnoea, 2) the rate of inappropriate discharges of patients with dyspnoea. The composite score is given by the square root of the sum of the squares of the two indicators.
<u>Data needed</u>	Dyspnoea at triage; appropriateness of admissions of patients with dyspnoea; appropriateness of discharges of patients with dyspnoea.
<u>Type</u>	Clinical appropriateness of care.
<u>Rationale</u>	Admission and discharge of patients with dyspnoea should be as appropriate as possible.
<u>Objective</u>	To reduce the score from the previous year's value (see appendix).
<u>Notes</u>	This indicator will only be proposed once the corresponding algorithm for assessing the appropriateness of admissions developed by Fenice has been validated.

Appendix

COMPOSITE INDICATOR

A composite indicator is defined as an overall numerical indicator that is able to express the performance of two simple indicators representing two separate aspects of the phenomenon of interest. The two simple indicators must be constructed in such a way that lower values correspond to more desirable situations in terms of the phenomenon itself. For example, when using a high-resource or risky diagnostic test, it is desirable that patients with a higher probability of having the suspected pathology be tested (and thus that there be a low percentage of patients carrying the pathology who are not tested, i.e., a low percentage of missed events), but at the same time it is desirable that patients with a lower probability not be tested (and thus that there be a low number of tests performed to detect a patient with the pathology of interest). Both of these indicators should have low values. The proposed composite indicator corresponds to the distance from the origin of the point representing the projection on a Cartesian system of the two simple indicators. The reduction of both simple indicators results in the reduction of the composite indicator. The interpretative scheme for the achievement of the objective could be as follows, to be defined more precisely, on a case-by-case basis, according to the specific phenomenon of interest.

CROWDING INDICATOR

The proposed crowding indicator aims to quantify the level of crowding in the emergency department in real time. The indicator is defined on 7 levels (from 1 - not crowded, to 7 - severely overcrowded), based on the waiting time of patients with minor or non-deferrable urgency, with code 3 or 4 at triage. While the average waiting time for code 1 or 2 patients does not change significantly as the number of patients present increases, given the urgency of admission of such patients, patients with lower priority codes are affected by an increase in time when there is crowding. In addition, given the low number of patients with code 5, such cases were excluded.

Data to be collected

In order to calculate the indicator, it is necessary to record the date and time of access to the ED, the time of the first medical or nursing assessment, and the priority code assigned at triage for each patient who entered the ED in a predefined time period (preferably in the previous year).

Calculation of the indicator

Separately for each ED and each hour, the total number of patients present is calculated, considering both waiting patients and patients being visited. Then, using a linear regression model, the relationship between the number of patients present and the waiting time for codes 3 and 4 is estimated. Seven waiting time categories are defined on the basis of clinically relevant time frames (<15, 15-30, 30-60, 60-90, 90-150, 150-210 and \geq 210 minutes) and the estimated models are used to calculate the thresholds of patients present corresponding, on average, to the time categories for each centre and time frame.

The estimated thresholds thus indicate the number of patients defining the 7 indicator categories. Since they are calculated on separately estimated models for each ED, they are centre-specific and can be applied to measure the degree of crowding at any given time.

The use of an indicator with centre-specific thresholds makes it possible to estimate crowding levels that can be compared between EDs with different characteristics and volumes of access. Although the levels are actually defined by different numbers of patients, a given level of the indicator corresponds to the same average waiting time for code 3 or 4 patients.